

THE USE OF AI IN ALTERNATIVE DISPUTE RESOLUTION IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the increasing digital usage in the legal industry, particularly in the context of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR). As human errors and disputes increase, the filing of cases has become a burden on judges. The article suggests that AI can be used in ADR to provide a quick solution to petty cases. The article also discusses the impact of new AI regulations on ADR, as it is already using AI in ADR and will continue to do so in the future. The article also explores the evolving landscape of dispute resolution in India, focusing on the integration of AI technologies. It examines the potential benefits and challenges of AI in dispute resolution, considering legal and cultural contexts. The article highlights the advantages of AI tools in mediation, such as efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and addressing biases. It also highlights key AI tools suitable for mediation, such as rule-based reasoning, machine learning, and consensus agreements. The challenges of AI integration, such as data privacy concerns and job displacement, are also explored. The article concludes by emphasizing the transformative impact of AI on dispute resolution and the need for legal professionals to embrace technological advancements to enhance the legal profession.

Keywords- Artificial intelligence (AI), online dispute resolution, Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

AI technology has the potential to improve the dispute resolution process by accurately analyzing problems and reducing time spent on arbitration. However, its use in arbitration remains limited due to challenges such as lack of understanding and transparency in AI decision-making. Research is crucial to understand the potential and challenges of AI technology in dispute resolution, and establishing an appropriate regulatory framework is essential for its security and reliability.

AI is used by Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) to deliver fair decisions to disputes, however prejudice in data sets and algorithms is still a source of concern. The application of AI in alternative dispute resolution (ADR) requires well-defined ethical and legal frameworks that address issues of informed consent, data privacy, and confidentiality. Regulations and guidelines that support equity and openness in the application of AI are also essential.

Arbitration and mediation are two examples of Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) processes that have grown in popularity as alternatives to traditional court proceedings for settling conflicts. Anticipating future resolutions of comparable disputes through machine learning and algorithms, predictive analytics is a subfield of artificial intelligence that is projected to have a major impact on alternative dispute resolution (ADR). Chatbots and virtual assistants driven by AI have the ability to guide parties through alternative dispute resolution (ADR) processes, making them more accessible to a wider spectrum of people.

However, there are potential drawbacks to AI integration in ADR, such as perpetuating existing biases within the legal system and concerns about transparency. As AI technology advances, it is essential for practitioners and policymakers to carefully consider the benefits and risks of AI integration in ADR and take measures to ensure its impartiality, transparency, and accountability.

II. The role of AI in enhancing Alternate Dispute Resolution mechanisms in India

In the past, Indian communities relied on village panchayats or councils of elders to settle disputes; this is where Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) got its start. However, the Arbitration and Conciliation Act of 1996 marked the official start of the use of ADR procedures in the late 20th century. This act brought India's dispute resolution practices into line with international norms by establishing a legislative framework for arbitration, mediation, and

conciliation. Ever since, the field of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) in India has experienced consistent expansion, thanks to the founding of specialist organizations like the International Centre for Alternative Dispute Resolution (ICADR), the Centre for Alternative Dispute Resolution (CADR), and the Indian Council of Arbitration (ICA).

These organizations are vital to the advancement of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) as they offer mediators and arbitrators training and certification, as well as support for ADR cases.

A significant change in how legal issues are resolved is highlighted by the government's initiative to support alternative dispute resolution (ADR) procedures. ADR procedures, like arbitration, conciliation, mediation, and judicial settlement, provide parties with more adaptable, effective, and cooperative ways to resolve disputes than only depending on the court system. These strategies not only free up the court system but also enable people and companies to come to amicable agreements that suit their particular situation.

ADR mechanisms are recognized and supported by the legal framework established by Section 89 of the Civil Procedure Code, 1908. This clause gives judges the authority to send cases for judicial settlement, arbitration, conciliation, mediation, or the novel method of resolving conflicts through Lok Adalat. Section 89 allows courts to consider alternatives to traditional litigation, especially when there is a chance for a settlement that can be reached amicably. This is because it acknowledges the importance of these alternative approaches.

The government's efforts to promote a mediation culture in India have reached a major turning point with the passing of the Mediation Act, 2023. Courts may now send cases for mediation, particularly those involving compoundable offenses and marriage conflicts, thanks to this legislation. The Mediation Act seeks to improve the efficacy and recognition of mediation as a feasible substitute for litigation by formalizing and streamlining the mediation process through the establishment of a statutory framework.

The government prioritizes alternative dispute resolution (ADR) procedures due to its understanding of their many advantages. ADR techniques provide a more cooperative and rapid approach to settling conflicts than traditional court proceedings, which can be confrontational and time-consuming. Parties to arbitration have more autonomy and influence over the process since they can choose the arbiter and the procedural guidelines. In a similar vein, mediation fosters candid conversation and compromise between parties with the support of an impartial

third-party mediator, enabling the investigation of innovative solutions catered to the parties' needs.

A key component of the government's program for judicial reforms is the government's attempts to fill judicial vacancies and strengthen the bench. The administration has adopted a diversified approach to judicial reform, as seen by appointments to higher judiciaries, increases in the sanctioned strength of judges, and initiatives like the creation of Fast Track Courts for cases involving serious crimes and vulnerable populations.

The effectiveness of arbitration as a technique for resolving disputes has been greatly increased by legislative changes, such as those made to the Arbitration and Conciliation Act. A major step toward positioning India as a Center for institutional arbitration has been taken with the creation of the India International Arbitration Centre (Centre) under the India International Arbitration Centre Act, 2019. India's use of mediation as a commonplace method of resolving disputes has reached a turning point with the passage of the Mediation Act, 2023. ADR procedures are being supported by the government through institutional and legislative changes. They recognize the importance of alternative conflict resolution techniques and make investments in the judicial system's infrastructure with the goal of ensuring that all citizens have prompt and efficient access to justice. This strategy increases the efficiency and efficacy of the legal system by enabling people and organizations to settle conflicts amicably.

III. Impact of COVID-19 on Alternate Dispute Resolution

ADR practitioners and the parties engaged in dispute resolution have faced both opportunities and problems as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic's substantial impact on ADR procedures. ADR practitioners now need to modify their procedures and methods to work well in virtual environments. COVID-19 has also had a significant impact on ADR through the change to online dispute resolution (ODR), enhanced accessibility, efficiency, and cost Savings.

In addition to creating a backlog of cases in court systems and alternative conflict resolution forums, the pandemic has also increased demand for alternative dispute resolution procedures by postponing the resolution of disputes. There may be more demand on ADR practitioners to accelerate case processing without sacrificing the fairness and quality of decisions. It is now necessary to comply with existing rules and regulations due to legal and regulatory concerns about jurisdictional issues, data privacy, confidentiality, and the enforceability of agreements made in online environments. Video conferencing technology has developed as the bridge that

connects ODR platforms, which have emerged as a means of resolving disagreements. The center for Alternate Dispute Resolution Excellence (CADRE), SAMA, the center for Online Dispute Resolution (CODR), and AGAMI are some of the trailblazing ODR platforms. These platforms offer a digital forum for conflict resolution, doing away with the requirement for in-person meetings by enabling parties to communicate via email or secure video chat.

ODR's acceptance in India has increased as a result of the pandemic, with practitioners and parties growing more at ease with conducting ADR procedures online. ADR procedures are now more accessible and efficient as a result, especially for people who live in various states or towns. Online court-annexed mediation has becoming a more popular way for Indian courts to settle conflicts amid the pandemic. Technology-enabled court-annexed mediation platforms have made it easier to resolve issues quickly and have decreased the backlog of unresolved cases in Indian courts.

India continues to have difficulties with its digital infrastructure, especially in its more rural and isolated regions. To provide fair access to ADR services for all societal segments, it is imperative to tackle these obstacles. The use of technology tools for online communication, document sharing, and virtual hearings, as well as overcoming linguistic and cultural barriers in virtual contacts, has required ADR practitioners in India to modify their procedures and approaches to suit virtual contexts.

A number of legal and regulatory frameworks, including those pertaining to jurisdiction, data protection, confidentiality, and the enforcement of online agreements, have also sprung up in India. Ensuring the legitimacy and integrity of virtual ADR hearings requires explicit guidelines and standards. To give ADR practitioners, attorneys, judges, and court employees the abilities and information they need to use virtual ADR platforms and carry out online procedures, capacity building and training initiatives are required.

The creation of fresh online dispute resolution platforms, AI-driven decision support tools, and virtual mediation and arbitration services catered to Indian stakeholders' requirements are examples of opportunities for innovation in ADR procedures and technology in India.

To sum up, the COVID-19 pandemic has expedited the assimilation of online dispute resolution technology and furnished practitioners with prospects to inventively adjust to novel obstacles and opportunities in the adept and efficient resolution of conflicts in virtual settings.

IV. Research Issue

Traditional conflict resolution methods often include inefficiencies, delays, and exorbitant prices, and human decision-making can introduce biases. Although integrating AI could fix these issues, doing so raises concerns about accountability, transparency, and ethical issues. This paper aims to critically evaluate the use of AI in dispute settlement, taking into account its benefits, limitations, and ethical concerns in addition to talking about the subjectivity of human decision-making.

V. Objective of the study

This research evaluates the possible advantages of artificial intelligence (AI) in terms of accessibility, accuracy, and efficiency in international conflict settlement. In order to solve these problems and optimize the advantages of AI in conflict resolution, it also highlights obstacles and limitations, investigates ethical considerations, and makes suggestions.

VI. Analysis and findings

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential to enhance the effectiveness, precision, and accessibility of international dispute resolution through the application of robots, data analytics, predictive modeling, distant alternatives, and AI. It can also be useful in decision support, case analysis, and legal research. However, issues with algorithmic bias, data privacy, security, transparency, and job displacement among lawyers are highlighted. Accountability, delegation of decision-making authority, and potential unintended consequences are ethical considerations that must be made to ensure fairness and honesty in conflict resolution methods.

AI is revolutionizing traditional conflict resolution systems by analyzing massive datasets and identifying patterns, making them more accurate, accessible, and efficient. Predictive analytics is one of the most notable ways AI has improved ADR, as it can predict how disputes will be resolved in the future by examining previous court cases and their results. This helps arbitrators and mediators make more informed decisions and helps parties understand possible outcomes.

Automated negotiation systems are a growing trend in ADR agreements using AI-powered systems as mediators. These systems process legal documents, create settlement agreements, and recommend the best negotiation approaches. AI accelerates the resolution process by streamlining the negotiating process and freeing disputants and mediators to focus on more

subtle aspects. AI innovations are also transforming case management by organizing and analysing case data more effectively, identifying important case features, highlighting possible problems, and suggesting procedural measures. AI integration in Online Dispute Resolution (ODR) platforms has proven beneficial, providing tools like machine learning models for outcome prediction, chatbots for initial legal aid, and efficient case processing algorithms. This makes ODR more accessible and user-friendly for those who may not have easy access to traditional legal services. To solve ethical issues, the application of AI in ADR needs to be strictly controlled, ensuring algorithm integrity and transparency in AI-driven decision-making. Future directions for AI in ADR include the application of more sophisticated machine learning models and natural language processing for better understanding of case narratives.

The increasing use of AI in ADR is transforming the role of arbitrators, mediators, and attorneys. They need to become more proficient in using AI tools, enhancing human judgment with data-driven insights. This shift in skill set involves a focus on technology competence alongside traditional legal and negotiating abilities. The public's perception and acceptance of AI in ADR will determine its success. To gain public trust, it is crucial to demonstrate the benefits, equity, and dependability of AI-driven dispute resolution techniques. This can be achieved through educational programs and open operations.

VII. Framework for Legislation

Although AI and its uses have been promoted by the Indian government, Big Data, AI, and machine learning are not specifically covered by any legislation in the country. In order to optimize the advantages of being a late adopter, the 2018 National Strategy of Artificial Intelligence intends to provide high-quality domestically developed digital capabilities in AI. The work of creating laws, guidelines, and regulations pertaining to the control and regulation of AI has already begun. AI's beneficial impact on online dispute settlement was acknowledged in an NITI Aayog report titled "Designing the Future of Dispute Resolution, 2021". In order to eliminate human bias and replace the existing paradigm of conflict settlement, the article underlined the significance of artificial intelligence (AI) in the development of India's electronic dispute settlement system. The legal system can greatly benefit from the integration of technology. For example, smart contracts that are computer-coded have the potential to automate enforceability through the transfer of rights and duties, thereby facilitating dispute resolution through blockchain arbitration. The UNCITRAL Convention on Electronic Communications in International Contracts of 2007 and the UNCITRAL Electronic Model

Law on Electronic Commerce of 1996 serve as the primary legal underpinnings for blockchain contracts.

VIII. Obstacles to AI implementation in ADR

AI systems are trained and data sets are operated. Artificial Intelligence has the potential to compromise the goals of the Arbitration.

Integrating AI into arbitration requires advanced technology development and training, which can be costly and time-consuming. However, it can improve human lives and impact labor markets and employment rates. Privacy rules are crucial in arbitration proceedings, as private information can be compromised by hackers and new software can lead to technical problems. AI's lack of logic, accountability, and secrecy can lead to trust issues among parties. Arbitration rulings follow a predetermined methodology, providing a rigid framework with limited flexibility. Each award includes a statement outlining the elements that went into the decision.

AI has the power to completely transform arbitrations and mediations, two forms of alternative dispute resolution (ADR). Nonetheless, a number of obstacles need to be cleared before AI is completely included into ADR processes. The lack of confidence that many people have in AI's ability to make impartial and fair decisions is one of the main obstacles. Additionally, the industry lacks standards and regulations, which makes it challenging for parties to plan ahead and know what to anticipate.

Finally, the effectiveness of AI in alternative dispute resolution (ADR) is not well studied, and decision-making processes that lack transparency can breed distrust and discontent. The shortage of qualified experts to create and execute AI systems for ADR is a result of the field's recent infancy.

IX. The meeting of ADR and AI

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming alternative dispute resolution (ADR) through increased speed and efficiency. Large data sets can be swiftly analyzed by AI systems, which can also spot trends and render unbiased judgments. This speeds up and lowers the cost of resolving disputes. In complex circumstances, this is especially helpful. In addition to helping to close the gap between parties and facilitate communication, AI systems can offer objective recommendations for settlement agreements. But integrating AI comes with its own set of

difficulties, including a lack of knowledge and trust in the technology. All parties involved must get education and training, and AI decision-making processes must be transparent in order to overcome this. The absence of standards and regulations in the industry is another difficulty. AI in ADR can be used consistently and predictably by establishing norms and rules, which will let parties prepare and know what to expect.

Notwithstanding these obstacles, AI has the potential to be a crucial ADR tool that promotes more equitable and efficient dispute resolution. It's crucial to remember that artificial intelligence (AI) is meant to assist, not replace, human decision-making. Though AI can offer recommendations and speed up, improve, and neutralize the process, humans should always make the final decision.

Jacob Turner highlights the difference between automated and autonomous systems in AI models, saying that although automated systems follow predetermined guidelines, autonomous systems can decide for themselves without human intervention. This distinction is essential to the establishment of legal and ethical norms. Whereas autonomous systems are more sophisticated and self-sufficient, automated systems are deterministic and follow instructions that have been written by humans.

AlphaGo's victory over the Go masters in 2017 is proof that artificial intelligence is a distinct phenomenon, particularly in the legal domain. The game is thought to be the hardest strategic game ever, dating back around 3,000 years. In fact, it is so challenging that children in South Korea and China are sent to special schools to learn how to play it. Artificial Intelligence can function independently in any area, but it excels in the legal sector.

In order for an arbitration to be decided, each party must submit their case to one or more arbitrators. After considering all available information, listening to both sides' arguments, reviewing pertinent case law, and weighing all relevant factors, the arbitrator issues a final decision known as a "award."

The award is final and binding, not because of the force of any state, but because the parties have agreed that it should be. Arbitration is a helpful technique for obtaining a final decision on a disagreement or series of conflicts without going to court.

AI was previously thought to be outside the purview of dispute resolution, particularly in arbitration, due to worries that it would lead to litigation in public courts about enforcement-

related issues. According to Lucas Bento, this resistance stems from the fact that advocacy robots have never been able to make decisions.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence presents a lot of opportunities for arbitration; however, it is critical to comprehend the ways in which it may be applied across a range of sectors, including the legal sector.

X. Decision making and Advantages of AI in ADR

There are three mental components that make up the human mind: the conscious, subconscious, and unconscious. In addition to the conscious and subconscious minds, the unconscious and external environment are also involved in the decision-making process. Unlike humans, artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms are designed to act independently and are not swayed by arbitrary factors. These programs are programmed by algorithms, which gives them a higher level of logic than decisions made by humans. Thus, in AI systems, rationality in decision-making is essential.

1. Arbitration procedures can be made much more efficient by using artificial intelligence (AI). AI can be used to appoint an unbiased third party to settle disputes without needless costs or delays because it is cognitively neutral and independent of outside influences. It can expedite the process by automating laborious data processing and legal investigation.
2. AI can also assist in removing mistakes in decision-making, documentation, translation, interpretation, and authority selection. AI can identify blind zones and offer solutions for minimizing them by being used at different times or for different tasks. Based on the information supplied by the disputing parties, AI is also capable of predicting outcomes.
3. AI can expedite the creation of awards by enabling parties to transfer funds between their bank accounts, guaranteeing that the award is followed. This can be accomplished by utilizing AI to send recall requests to the appropriate authorities and parties in order to ensure that the award is being complied with.

Finally, through error elimination, outcome prediction, and speedy award construction, AI may greatly increase the efficiency of arbitration procedures. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has the potential to enhance the efficiency and economy of the arbitration process, resulting in improved dispute settlement outcomes.

XI. Implementing AI in Legal Decisions: The Future Outlook for Litigation and ADR

Artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly advanced the field of legal decision-making, offering numerous benefits to legal professionals. Artificial Intelligence has the ability to deliver insights to assist in decision-making, automate repetitive operations, and evaluate enormous volumes of legal data. Legislation, rules, case law, and legal opinions are just a few of the many legal documents that Hon. Judges may analyzing and classify with the help of AI-powered platforms. AI algorithms are able to evaluate risks, anticipate case outcomes, spot patterns and trends in past legal data, and assist in decision-making.

Utilizing machine learning algorithms to find and extract pertinent information from contracts, agreements, and other legal documents, AI may also help with document review and due diligence procedures. Insightful statistics on previous decisions, case outcomes, and legal matter trends can be produced by AI platforms through analytics and visualizations.

The process of locating and classifying pertinent electronic data for legal reasons can be automated with the help of AI-powered e-discovery systems. In order to uncover pertinent evidence, AI systems may scan emails, papers, and other digital assets. This saves time and effort compared to manual inspection. Artificial intelligence (AI) tools may examine and compare contracts more quickly by extracting important terminology, clauses, and obligations from them.

AI can help ensure and monitor adherence to legal and regulatory standards. AI systems have the capacity to examine enormous volumes of data, including communications and financial transactions, in order to find possible compliance issues.

A procedure known as online dispute resolution (ODR) involves settling conflicts through the use of digital tools like online forums, video conferencing, and messaging. ODR can be applied in a variety of situations, such as family law cases, consumer complaints, and commercial conflicts. It offers an alternative to conventional dispute resolution techniques like litigation or arbitration. Benefits include quick accessibility, ease, adaptability, and transparency are provided by the intimate relationship between ODR and AI.

Judges are attempting to have a deeper comprehension of the technology and its ramifications as they become more aware of the role that artificial intelligence plays in court cases. Predicting legal outcomes is a significant area of application for AI in the legal system. Artificial

intelligence (AI) algorithms are capable of analyzing vast volumes of data and making forecasts regarding the chances of a legal case succeeding or failing. Judges are cognizant of the algorithms' shortcomings and possible biases, though.

The use of AI-generated evidence in court is another area where judges are becoming aware of the function of AI. Judges are trying to establish guidelines for assessing the validity and admissibility of AI-generated evidence as they become more conversant with the technology underlying it.

In order to maintain fairness and openness in the legal system, judges are also striving to restrict the use of AI. In order to ensure that AI is used without violating people's rights, they are creating precise legal foundations for its application in court cases. As more cases use AI technology, judges and other legal professionals are becoming more interested in learning about the technology and its ramifications, which is generally increasing the judiciary's recognition of AI.

XII. The Emerging AI Landscape in Alternate Dispute Resolution

Artificial intelligence (AI) is a transformative force that is revolutionizing various industries, including law. It is expected to become integral to AI-DR (Artificial Intelligence in Dispute Resolution), which will address longstanding issues such as backlog, inefficiencies, high costs, complexity, and inherent biases in the dispute resolution domain. However, AI also introduces new challenges and complexities, such as concerns over new biases, diminished privacy, and a lack of transparency.

Legitimacy serves as a cornerstone in the realm of dispute resolution, and it is crucial to understand disputants' perceptions regarding the tasks they trust AI to handle, the types of cases suitable for AI involvement, and the conditions under which AI intervention is acceptable. Algorithms currently play a prominent role in criminal justice settings, particularly in decisions impacting defendants' liberty, but their utilization in small-scale, repetitive, and straightforward civil disputes remains limited.

The rise of AI-DR underscores a broader trend of boundary erosion within the dispute resolution landscape. The integration of alternative dispute resolution (ADR) mechanisms into courts blurred the lines between formal and informal resolution processes, and the adoption of online dispute resolution (ODR) further dissolved distinctions between online and offline

arenas. With AI now permeating these domains, the boundaries continue to diminish, as technology and automation become integral components across various stages of dispute resolution, displacing roles traditionally reserved for human agents.

The future landscape of AI in Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) is likely to be characterized by significant advancements in technology, changes in the way disputes are resolved, and shifts in the role of human decision-makers. This includes the emergence of sophisticated AI-driven platforms, personalized dispute resolution solutions, virtual and augmented reality mediation, blockchain-based dispute resolution mechanisms, AI-powered decision support tools, cross-border dispute resolution platforms, continuous learning and improvement, ethical and regulatory considerations, and a commitment to balancing the benefits of AI with the preservation of human judgment and values in resolving conflicts.

In conclusion, the future landscape of AI in ADR holds the promise of more accessible, efficient, and equitable dispute resolution processes, empowered by innovative technologies and guided by ethical principles and best practices. However, realizing this vision will require collaboration among stakeholders, ongoing research and development efforts, and a commitment to balancing the benefits of AI with the preservation of human judgment and values in resolving conflicts.

XIII. Artificial intelligence working method in ADR

AI has two applications in alternative dispute resolution (ADR): as a neutral third party and as a useful tool. AI can help with research, standard drafting, document analysis, lying detection, damage assessment, consequence estimation, and remedy suggestion. This expedites the ADR procedure and enables AI to be consulted advisory-only by human decision-makers. As an alternative, AI can explore its database to find the offer that most closely resembles its model solution, enabling both sides to present their finest proposals. This architecture promotes reasonable offers, removing potential roadblocks for AI to select the optimal offer.

XIV. Conclusion

Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to enhance accessibility, accuracy, and efficiency in international dispute resolution. However, balancing ethical considerations with the use of AI requires collaboration between legislators, technologists, and ethicists. Research on algorithmic bias, accountability, and openness is necessary to ensure AI complements human

judgment. AI can provide predictive insights, automate conversations, and improve case management, revolutionizing the field.

To fully incorporate AI into the legal system, additional work is needed. AI's effectiveness depends on the quality of data processed and the algorithm used. The legal industry must adapt to the times and capitalize on AI. AI is intended to simplify, speed up, and deliver efficient legal services, not to undermine or replace the legal profession.

AI has the potential to significantly improve Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) by ensuring reliable, fair, and inclusive systems. However, public trust in AI-driven justice systems remains a concern, as justice is often seen as a human ideal. AI is not intended to replace or diminish lawyers' role, but rather to be a powerful tool, streamlining tasks, improving efficiency, and enabling lawyers to provide better legal services. The most effective approach is to embrace AI strategically, leveraging the complementary strengths of humans and machines.

Arbitration must change from a conservative arena to one that is compatible with the modern legal system. With the introduction of Covid-19 and the recent technological advancements in the legal field, arbitration is sure to keep up. Arbitration could become more equitable, quicker, and more seamless with the application of AI. That being said, states need to get ready for the problems that lie ahead and apply AI progressively and steadily. High-quality data input and algorithmic accuracy are critical to the success of AI-assisted arbitration. Evaluation of the algorithmic structure and quality control of the data input are required. The advent of these new technological procedures doesn't diminish or threaten the traditional character of the arbitral process; rather, with the right application of technology, it expands its potential. Artificial Intelligence (AI) in arbitration is rapidly becoming into a crucial aid with enormous potential for advancement and use.
